

IMPROVING MECHANISMS OF LITERACY SKILLS DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING THE HERITAGE OF OUR ANCESTORS

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Annotation: This article provides information about innovative methods of improving the quality of education and the role of primary school teachers. Also, it was thought about improving the study of the heritage of ancestors and improving the functions of developing literacy skills in primary education.

Key words: literacy, education, religion, knowledge, personality, spirituality, identity, psychology, society, culture, development, patriotism, humanitarianism, communication.

The introduction of the National Curriculum developed on the basis of advanced international experiences into school education is defined as the most important task of raising intellectually literate young generation with high spirituality, modern knowledge and skills, and independent thinking.

It is known that literacy is one of the most important aspects of the development of the nation, and it is not only a separate branch of the education system, but a primary issue in all spheres of the state. At the 10th session of UNESCO held in Paris in 1958, in order to unify the concept of literacy in all countries, it was agreed to count as literate those who can understand and read writing and describe their daily life in writing. At the UNESCO General Conference in 1966, September 8 was designated as International Literacy Day.

Literacy is one of the indicators of the cultural level of the population; oral and written speech that conforms to the norms of the literary language of a person; be able to read simple texts or read and write them; perfect knowledge in a specific field; personal and life qualities; it is the level of ownership of skills such as increasing the social, political, scientific, cultural and spiritual level of a person at various stages of the development of society [1].

The student's level of literacy skills is evaluated through his ability to complete educational tasks and the presentation of his written works. A student's literacy is developed in three stages, that is, emergent literacy, formal education and literacy.

Developing literacy, formal education, and literacy are mentioned as stages of student literacy development.

Developing Literacy. The learner is exposed to a variety of information and needs to interpret and process the uses and meanings of words. Until the first grade, the child is introduced to books, advertisements, brochures and various printed letters and symbols. It is reflected in the child's ability to flip through the book, use it, and know what the symbols in it mean.

Formal Education. Begins in the early years of school, where students acquire formal skills that enable literacy. Also, skills that are initially self-learning (learning to read and write) become tools for learning other knowledge.

Literacy. Literacy is a necessary skill acquired by a student through formal education and is gradually used in daily life experiences throughout the course of learning [2].

Literacy is a tool that ensures the further development of the student, and it has been proven that it is a vital necessity that provides an opportunity to develop knowledge, to understand and follow one's rights and duties, to use knowledge in all areas, and to increase life experience. In modern society, "literacy" is often understood as the ability to write in accordance with grammar and spelling standards, without errors, and the mastery of literacy skills in the primary school is considered the most basic and most important. For this reason, this literacy acts as a "key" to all other literacy in the field.

The educational system of our country is aimed at making all strata of the population literate, and the quality implementation of this responsible task is entrusted to the school. One of the factors in the development of literacy skills of a young student is their conscious, fluent reading skills through the careful assimilation of the heritage of ancestors on the basis of scientific and artistic sources during the educational process. Also, cases of development of oral and written speech, literacy skills are understood.

Since ancient times, literacy has been considered one of the most beautiful human qualities. Hazrat Navoi's works such as "Muhokamat ul-lughatayn", "Mahbub-ul Qulub", "Lison ut-tayr", "Savodi ta'lim" of Munis spoke about the sensitivity and importance of the issue of student literacy. The work "Boburnoma" contains information about Babur's reforms to ensure the purity of the language.

The process of learning the heritage of ancestors given in the primary education program, along with the development of students' literacy skills, it was found in the process of testing that personal qualities such as patriotism,

humanitarianism, awareness of national identity, respect for values are formed in them.

As a result of the skills acquired in the 1st grade literacy period, students gradually acquire the skills of reading texts and complex words related to the heritage of their ancestors, understanding their meaning, and analyzing their content. In particular, they can be analyzed as follows:

- the first stage, learning to read;
- second stage, expressive and fluent reading;
- the third stage, reading with comprehension;
- the fourth stage, conscious reading;
- fifth stage, work on complex texts;
- the sixth stage, communication formation [3].

Pedagogical-psychological features of developing the literacy skills of students based on axiological approaches based on the study of the heritage of ancestors in primary grades have unique opportunities. Also, this process is one of the main factors that ensure continuous self-development of a person throughout his life.

Pedagogical and psychological factors affecting the development of literacy skills of primary school students in the process of studying the heritage of ancestors are given below:

- Evaluating one's own work;
- Respecting the person, preserving his dignity, fully demonstrating and developing his potential and abilities;
- Comparing oneself with others;
- Based on axiological and deontological approaches and values;
- Ability to create a creative process;
- Pedagogical cooperation in mental, physical, intellectual, moral development is a priority and ability to compromise;
- Interest in knowing and analyzing religious and worldly knowledge;
- The need to acquire new knowledge [4].

In conclusion, the analysis of the scientific literature conducted in order to determine the state of development of literacy skills of elementary school students in the process of studying the heritage of ancestors proved that literacy is the most important factor for a person as a life skill. It is the main task to develop the literacy of students from the primary grades, especially to study examples of the heritage of ancestors, to achieve social and spiritual and moral values, harmonious relations with the world. At the same time, in order to

understand the internal unity of different systems of values and standards, it allowed to interpret it as a sub-competence of value-worldview with its own characteristics, such as the development and realization of a person's own spiritual world.

Also, the thorough acquisition of literacy skills by students from the primary grade will allow to increase the indicators of the cultural level of the population in the future. At the same time, it leads to a person's ability to speak and write in accordance with the norms of the literary language, the ability to read and write them, and to have excellent knowledge in a specific field. It is also important for having personal and life skills, skills for improving the social, political, scientific, cultural and spiritual level of a person at various stages of society's development.

References:

1. Husanova M. Boshlang'ich sinflarda o'qish savodxonligini shakllantirish // "Ijodkor o'qituvchi" jurnali, Volume 2, № 24. 2022. -B.760.
2. Safarova Sh.T. Ta'lim tizimida boshlang'ich ta'limning o'rni va ahamiyati // "Ustozlar uchun" jurnali, Volume 53, № 3. 2024. -B.70.
3. Musurmonqulov J. Po'latov D. Maktab ta'limida o'quvchilarni tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonligini oshirilishi // "Zamonaviy dunyoda pedagogika va psixologiya: Nazariy va amaliy izlanishlar", Volume 2, № 3. 2023. -B.33.
4. Yo'ldosheva N.U. Yoqubov E.Y. Boshlang'ich sinflarda tarbiyaviy ishlarning ahamiyati // O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali, Volume 2, № 15. 2023. -B.110.
5. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Manifestations of Moral Threats in the Ideosphere of Uzbekistan and Their Prevention Strategy. *Asian Journal of Basic Science & Research*, 5(1), 103-108.
6. Sobirovich, T. B. (2023). Basic Criteria for Building the Third Renaissance in Uzbekistan. *Asian Journal of Applied Science and Technology (AJAST)*, 7(1), 149-
7. Sobirovich, T. B., & Norman, Z. D. M. (2023). Harmony of National and Universal Values in Uzbekistan. *Harmony*, 7(1), 08-16.